

TIM SHERRATT

@wragge

EXPLORING DIGITAL COLLECTIONS WITH THE GLAM WORKBENCH

**THESE
SLIDES**

<https://slides.com/wragge/glam-workbench-estonia/>

COLLECTIONS AS DATA?

See also: <https://collectionsasdata.github.io/>

SEARCH IS FAMILIAR

TROVE

ABOUT HELP NEWS PARTNERS SIGN UP LOGIN

Explore

Categories

Community

Research

First Australians

Home / Search results

All Newspapers & Gazettes Magazines & Newsletters Images, Maps & Artefacts Research & Reports Books & Libraries Diaries, Letters & Archives Music, Audio & Video People & Organisations Websites Lists

Newspapers & Gazettes

radio

Advanced search

NEWSPAPERS & GAZETTES

3,430,613 total results Sort by: Relevance

REFINE YOUR RESULTS

Type

- Newspaper (3m)
- Gazette (36k)

Place

- New South Wales (1m)
- Queensland (691k)
- Western Australia (409k)
- Victoria (386k)
- South Australia (311k)
- ACT (180k)

Show more

RADIO.

Article - The Longreach Leader (Qld. : 1923 - 1954) Friday 26 September 1924 - Page 14

... prophetic imagination. Solleys Ltd. advertise in this issue that they are licensed dealers in all **radio** ... **RADIO** Are you interested in wireless? Have you considered what is in the,air for you, and at your ... 111 words

Text corrected by 1 Voluntrove

RADIO.

Article - The West Australian (Perth, WA : 1879 - 1954) Tuesday 15 September 1925 - Page 6

... **RADIO**. Mr. H. Broughton Jensen, who was recently engaged to make an examina-tion of the **Radio** mime ... 68 words

Text corrected by 1 Voluntrove

BUT WHAT ABOUT THE OTHER 3M?

The screenshot shows the Trove website interface. At the top, the Trove logo is centered, with navigation links for ABOUT, HELP, NEWS, PARTNERS, SIGN UP, and LOGIN to the right. Below the logo is a horizontal menu with categories: Explore, Categories, Community, Research, and First Australians. A red line with circular markers starts from the 'First Australians' category and points down towards a large red 'L' shape. Below the menu is a breadcrumb trail: Home / Search results. A secondary navigation bar lists various content types: All, Newspapers & Gazettes, Magazines & Newsletters, Images, Maps & Artefacts, Research & Reports, Books & Libraries, Manuscripts, Letters & Archives, Music, Audio & Video, People & Organisations, Websites, and Lists. The 'Newspapers & Gazettes' category is selected and underlined. The main heading is 'Newspapers & Gazettes'. A search bar contains the text 'radio'. To the right of the search bar is a magnifying glass icon and the text 'Advanced search'. Below the search bar, the results section is titled 'NEWSPAPERS & GAZETTES'. It shows '3,430,613 total results' circled in red, followed by a 'Sort by' dropdown menu set to 'Relevance'. On the right side, there is a 'REFINE YOUR RESULTS' section with two filters: 'Type' (Newspaper (3m), Gazette (36k)) and 'Place' (New South Wales (1m), Queensland (691k), Western Australia (409k), Victoria (386k), South Australia (311k), ACT (180k)). Below the filters is a 'Show more' link. The main results area displays two article snippets. The first snippet is titled 'RADIO.' and is from 'The Longreach Leader (Qld. : 1923 - 1954)' dated 'Friday 26 September 1924 - Page 14'. The text of the snippet reads: '... prophetic imagination. Solleys Ltd. advertise in this issue that they are licensed dealers in all radio ... RADIO Are you interested in wireless? Have you considered what is in the,air for you, and at your ... 111 words'. Below the snippet is a link 'Text corrected by 1 Voluntrove'. The second snippet is also titled 'RADIO.' and is from 'The West Australian (Perth, WA : 1879 - 1954)' dated 'Tuesday 15 September 1925 - Page 6'. The text of the snippet reads: '... RADIO. Mr. H. Broughton Jensen, who was recently engaged to make an examina-tion of the Radio mime ... 68 words'. Below this snippet is also a link 'Text corrected by 1 Voluntrove'.

SAME SEARCH

DIFFERENT VIEW

MORE SEARCHES

DIFFERENT QUESTIONS!

APIS
DATA DUMPS
CSVS
FULL TEXT
IMAGES

COLLECTIONS
AS
DATA

**APIS
DATA DUMPS
CSVS
FULL TEXT
IMAGES**

**COLLECTIONS
AS
DATA**

GLAM WORKBENCH

NOT JUST HOW,
BUT WHY...

- **possibilities** – why should I be interested?
- **starting points** – can you give me an example I can use?
- **pathways** – where do I go next?

628
CSV FILES

CSV files from Australian GLAM organisations
harvested from government data portals

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/glam-data-portals/>

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/csv-explorer/>

GLAM CSV Explorer

Cultural institutions are making collection data available as machine readable downloads. But how can researchers explore the shape and meaning of this data? How do they know what types of questions they can ask?

This notebook provides a quick overview of CSV-formatted data files, particularly those created by GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums). The list of CSV files from Australian GLAM insitutions provided below [was harvested from state and national government data portals](#). You can select a file from the list or upload your own.

The CSV Explorer looks at each column in the selected CSV file and tries to identify the type of data inside. It then attempts to tell you something useful about it. There's some more details about the process below.

Given all the possible variations in recording and formatting data, there will be errors. But hopefully this will provide you with a useful starting point for further exploration.

Select CSV Enter CSV url Upload CSV

Select a CSV file:

Filter by organisation:

Filter by dataset:

Analyse CSV Clear

GLAM Workbench

Search

GLAM-Workbench
40 Repositories

GLAM Workbench

- Home
- About >
- Help >
- Data sources >
- GLAM Labs
- Trove >
- DigitalNZ
- Archives >
- Libraries >
- Web Archives
- Museums >
- Government >
- Suggest a topic
- Ask a question

chat on [gitter](#)

Welcome to the GLAM Workbench

Here you'll find a collection of tools, tutorials, examples, and hacks to help you work with data from galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (the GLAM sector). The primary focus is Australia and New Zealand, but new collections are being added all the time. Let me know if there's some GLAM data you'd like me to explore – [suggestions](#) are always welcome!

Quick start

The resources in the GLAM Workbench are created and shared as Jupyter notebooks. Jupyter lets you combine narrative text and live code in an environment that encourages you to learn and explore. Jupyter notebooks run in your browser, and you can get started without installing any software – just click on a few links!

Here's how to find your way around the GLAM Workbench and open open up a notebook.

Table of contents

- Quick start
- What is GLAM data?
- What can I do with GLAM data?
- Do I need to be able to code?
- Other GLAM related notebooks

Australian Woman's Mirror 13 November 1984, p. 39

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/>

IS

- tools, tutorials, examples, hacks
- live code
- editable, reusable, hackable
- openly licensed

IS NOT

- coding 101
- finished or perfect

POWERED BY JUPYTER

<https://jupyter.org/>

JUPYTER NOTEBOOKS

WHY JUPYTER?

- Computing in your browser
- A **computational narrative** – combine text, images, code & more
- A standard format – use on different platforms
- See [Introduction to Jupyter Notebooks](#)

GLAM EXAMPLES

**JUPYTER
NOTEBOOKS**

- [Biblioteca Virtual Miguel de Cervantes Labs](#)
- [British Library](#)
- [National Library of Scotland](#)
- [Library of Congress](#)

JUPYTER CAN BE...

**NOT JUST
NOTEBOOKS**

- used on multiple platforms
- presented in different formats
- changed by extensions
- tailored to different users

USE JUPYTER TO...

**NOT JUST
NOTEBOOKS**

- create tutorials
- develop tools
- harvest data
- share code snippets
- document an API
- visualise a dataset
- hack an interface
- move data around

EXAMPLES

DOCUMENT DATA SOURCES

WEB ARCHIVE APIS

Timegates

Timegates let you query a web archive for the capture closest to a specific date. You do this by supplying your target date as the `Accept-Datetime` value in the headers of your request.

For example, if you wanted to query the Australian Web Archive to find the version of `http://nla.gov.au/` that was captured as close as possible to 1 January 2001, you'd set the `Accept-Datetime` header to header to 'Fri, 01 Jan 2010 01:00:00 GMT' and request the url:

```
https://web.archive.org/awa/http://nla.gov.au/
```

A `get` request will return the captured page, but if all you want is the url of the archived page you can use a `head` request and extract the information you need from the response headers. Try this:

```
In [3]: response = requests.head('https://web.archive.org/awa/http://nla.gov.au/', headers={'Accept-Datetime': 'Fri, 01 Jan 20:
response.headers
```

```
Out[3]: {'Server': 'nginx', 'Date': 'Fri, 22 May 2020 02:40:23 GMT', 'Content-Length': '0', 'Connection': 'keep-alive', 'L
```

The request above returns the following headers:

```
{
  'Server': 'nginx',
  'Date': 'Wed, 06 May 2020 04:34:50 GMT',
  'Content-Length': '0', 'Connection': 'keep-alive',
  'Location': 'https://web.archive.org/awa/20100205144227/http://nla.gov.au/',
  'Link': '<http://nla.gov.au/>; rel="original", <https://web.archive.org/awa/http://nla.gov.au/>; rel="timegate"
  'Vary': 'accept-datetime'
}
```

The `Link` parameter contains the Memento information. You can see that it's actually providing information on four types of link:

- the `original` url (ie the url that was archived) - `<http://nla.gov.au/>`
- the `timegate` for the harvested url (which is what we just used) - `<https://web.archive.org/awa/http://nla.gov.au/>`
- the `timemap` for the harvested url (we'll look at this below) - `<https://web.archive.org/awa/timemap/link/http://nla.gov.au/>`
- the `memento` - `<https://web.archive.org/awa/20100205144227mp_/http://nla.gov.au/>`

The `memento` link is the capture closest in time to the date we requested. In this case there's only about a month's difference, but of course this will depend on how frequently a url is captured. Opening the link will display the capture in the web archive. As we'll see below, some systems provide additional links such as `first memento`, `last memento`, `prev memento`, and `next memento`.

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/web-archives/>

EXPLORE AN API

(collections in time & space)

NATIONAL
MUSEUM OF
AUSTRALIA

GLAM Workbench

- Home
- About ▾
- Help ▾
- Data sources ▾
- Trove ▾
- DigitalNZ
- Archives ▾
- Libraries ▾
- Museums ^
 - [National Museum of Australia](#)
 - Te Papa
- Government ▾
- Suggest a topic

chat on [gitter](#)

National Museum of Australia collection

The National Museum of Australia provides access to its [collection data through an API](#). As well as collection items, data is available for parties, places, media, and more.

You'll need an [API key](#) for serious exploration.

[Explore live on Binder](#)

Tips, tools, and examples

Harvest records from the NMA API

If you're going to do any large-scale analysis of the NMA collection data, you probably want to harvest it all using the API and save it locally. This notebook helps you do just that. It harvests records in the [simple JSON format](#) and saves them as they are to a file-based database using TinyDB.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)

Exploring object records

In this notebook we'll have a preliminary poke around in the object data harvested from the NMA Collection API. I'll focus here on the basic shape/stats of the data, with a deeper dive into the `additionalType` and `extent` fields. Can we find the biggest object in the collection?

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)

Table of contents

- Tips, tools, and examples
 - Harvest records from the NMA API
 - Exploring object records
 - Explore collection objects over time
 - Explore places associated with collection objects
- Cite as

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/nma/>

EXPLORE AN API

(collections in time & space)

NATIONAL
MUSEUM OF
AUSTRALIA

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/nma/>

EXPLORE AN API

(collections in time & space)

NATIONAL
MUSEUM OF
AUSTRALIA

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/nma/>

AN API EXAMPLE

MUSEUMS
VICTORIA

A random item from the Museum of Victoria

```
[67]: import requests
import random
from IPython.display import Image, display, HTML
import ipywidgets as widgets

[36]: SEARCH_URL = 'https://collections.museumsvictoria.com.au/api/search'

[72]: def display_random(b):
out.clear_output()
params = {
    'query': '',
    'sort': 'random',
    'hasimages': 'yes'
}
response = requests.get(SEARCH_URL, params=params)
record = random.choice(response.json())
with out:
    display(HTML(f'<h3>{record["displayTitle"]}</h3>'))
    display(Image(url=record['media'][0]['small']['uri']))
    display(HTML(f'<a href="https://collections.museumsvictoria.com.au/{record["id"]}">More info...</a>'))

go = widgets.Button(description='Randomise!')
out = widgets.Output()
go.on_click(display_random)
display(go)
display(out)
```

Randomise!

Proof Coin - 1/2 Cent, British Caribbean Territories, 1955

[More info...](#)

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/museumsvictoria/>

PACKAGING DATA

(create collections of newspaper articles)

TROVE NEWSPAPER HARVESTER

Enter your search query

Use the [Trove web interface](#) to construct your search. Remember that the harvester will get **all** of the matched results, not just the first 2,000 you see in the web interface. Once you're happy with your search, just copy the url and paste it below.

Query url:

Set harvest options

By default the harvester only saves the metadata (date, page, title, newspaper etc) from the search results. If you want to save the full text content of each article, just check the `Text` box. You can also save PDF copies of every article by checking the `PDF` option, but be warned that this will slow down your harvest and generate large download files. If you want to save PDFs from large harvests, you're probably better off installing and running the harvester on your own computer.

- Save full text
- Save PDFs (this can be slow)

[Start harvest](#)

Once your harvest is complete a link will appear to download the results as a single, zipped file. See [this notebook](#) for more information about the contents and format of the results folder.

You can also start to explore your results [using this notebook](#).

Created by [Tim Sherratt \(@wragge\)](#) as part of the [GLAM Workbench project](#).

If you think this project is worthwhile you can [support it on Patreon](#).

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-harvester/>

EXTRACT METADATA

(no API? you can always try screen-scraping!)

GLAM Workbench

- Home
- About ▾
- Help ▾
- Data sources ▾
- Trove ▾
- DigitalNZ
- Archives ^
 - National Archives of Australia
 - RecordSearch**
 - White Australia Policy archives
 - ASIO archives
 - NSW State Archives
 - National Archives of NZ ▾
 - Queensland State Archives
- Libraries ▾
- Museums ▾
- Government ▾
- Suggest a topic

chat on gitter

RecordSearch

RecordSearch is the online collection database of the National Archives of Australia. Based on the [series system](#), RecordSearch provides rich, contextual information about series, items, agencies, and functions.

Unfortunately RecordSearch doesn't provide access to machine-readable data through an API, so we have to resort to screen scraping. The notebooks here all make use of the [RecordSearch Tools library](#) to handle the scraping.

If you plan to `git clone` this repository, make sure you include the `--recurse-submodules` option. This will grab the RecordSearch Tools code along with the notebooks.

[Explore live on Binder](#)

Tools, tips, and examples

Harvest items from a search in RecordSearch

Ever searched for items in RecordSearch and wanted to save the results as a CSV file, or in some other machine-readable format? This notebook walks you through the process of creating, managing, and saving item searches – all the way from search terms to downloadable dataset. You can even download all the images from items that have been digitised! And if you want to harvest series with more than 20,000 items, some strategies for this are included as well.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)

Table of contents

Tools, tips, and examples

- Harvest items from a search in RecordSearch
- Harvest files with the access status of 'closed'
- Harvesting functions from the RecordSearch interface
- How many of the functions are actually used?
- Harvest agencies associated with all functions
- Download the contents of a digitised file
- Get a list of agencies associated with a function
- Who's responsible?
- DFAT Cable Finder
- Cite as

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/recordsearch/>

EXTRACT METADATA

(no API? you can always try screen-scraping!)

5. Harvesting a complete set of (less than 20,000) results

Ok, we've learnt how to create a search and get back some data, but only getting the first 20 results is not so useful. What if our search contains hundreds or thousands of items? How do we get them all?

To save everything, we have to loop through each page in the result set, saving the results as we go. The functions below do just that.

But wait! You might have noticed that RecordSearch only displays results for searches that return fewer than 20,000 items. Because the screen scraper is just extracting details from the RecordSearch web pages, the 20,000 limit applies here as well. If your search has more than 20,000 results, you'll need to narrow it down using additional parameters.

The main function below is `harvest_items()`. You just give it any of the search parameters listed above. It will loop through all the pages in the result set, saving the items to a simple JSON database using TinyDB.

The database will be created in the `data` directory. It's name will include a timestamp, identifying the time at which the harvest was started. For example `db-items-1567492794.json`. There are more functions for using and managing the db files below.

```
In [303]: def get_total_results(client, **kwargs):
          ...
          Get the total number of results returned by a search.
          ...
          try:
              # Get the first page of results, passing digitised=False to speed things up
              results = client.search(digitised=False, **kwargs)

              # Get the total number of results
              total = results['total_results']

              # Uh oh there are more than 20,000 results
              except TooManyError:
                  print('There are more than 20,000 results.')
                  total = None
          return total

def harvest_items(start=1, db_path=None, check_duplicates=False, **kwargs):
    ...
    Harvest items from a search and save them to a database.
    Supply any of the search parameters listed above.

    Set check_duplicates to True if you want to check for possible duplicates (probably not necessary in most cases).
    ...
    # Initiate the client
    client = RSSearchClient()

    # Get the total number of results returned by this search
    total_results = get_total_results(client, **kwargs)
```

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/recordsearch/>

TROVE JOURNALS

DOWNLOAD TEXT

(a bit of API, a bit of screen-scraping)

Download the OCRd text for ALL the digitised journals in Trove!

Putting together the [list of journals created by this notebook](#) with the [code in this notebook](#), you can download the OCRd text from every digitised journal. If you're going to try this, you'll need a lots of patience and lots of disk space. Needless to say, don't try this on a cloud service like Binder.

Fortunately you don't have to do it yourself, as I've already run the harvest and made all the text files available. See below for details.

I repeat, **you probably don't want to do this yourself**. The point of this notebook is really to document the methodology used to create the repository.

If you really, really do want to do it yourself, you should first [generate an updated list of digitised journals](#).

Here's a harvest I prepared earlier...

I last ran this harvest in July 2020. Here are the results:

- 397 journals had OCRd text available for download
- OCRd text was downloaded from 26,234 journal issues
- About 6gb of text was downloaded

Note that, unlike previous harvests, this one excluded periodicals with the format 'government publication' – so the total amount harvested has decreased. Government publications are actually spread across both the books and journals zone, so I'm planning to do a separate harvest just for them.

The list of digital journals with OCRd text is available both as [human-readable list](#) and a [CSV formatted spreadsheet](#).

The complete collection of text files for all the journals can be downloaded [from this repository on CloudStor](#).

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-journals/>

DOWNLOAD IMAGES

(a bit of API, a bit of screen-scraping)

TROVE
JOURNALS

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-journals/>

VISUALISE SEARCHES

(asking historical questions with search facets)

Visualise Trove newspaper searches over time

This notebook helps you zoom out and explore how the number of Trove newspaper articles in your search results varies over time by using the `decade` and `year` facets. We then combine this approach with other search facets to see how we can slice a set of results up in different ways to investigate historical changes.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-newspapers/>

VISUALISE SEARCHES

(asking historical questions with search facets)


```
In [38]: # Make total results chart
chart9 = make_chart_totals(df_illtypes_merged, 'ill_type', 'Type')

# Make proportions chart
chart10 = make_chart_proportions(df_illtypes_merged, 'ill_type', 'Type')

# Shorthand way of concatenating the two charts (note there's only one legend)
chart9 & chart10
```


And there we have it – interesting to see the rapid increase in photos from the 1920s on.

VISUALISE SEARCHES

(asking historical questions with search facets)

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-newspapers/>

SEEING CHANGE

(screenshots over time)

WEB
ARCHIVES

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/web-archives/>

SEEING CHANGE

(text in web pages)

WEB
ARCHIVES

<p>The word "Anzac" has been a part of Australian thought, language, and life since 25 April 1915. Devised by a signaller in Egypt as a useful acronym for "Australian and New Zealand Army Corps", it quickly became a word with many uses and meanings.</p>	75	<p>The word "Anzac" has been a part of Australian thought, language, and life since 25 April 1915. Devised by a signaller in Egypt as a useful acronym for "Australian and New Zealand Army Corps", it quickly became a word with many uses and meanings.</p>	
<p>places: notably "Anzac area" on Gallipoli and "Anzac Cove" itself</p>	n	78	<p>places: notably "Anzac area" on Gallipoli and "Anzac Cove" itself</p>
<p>The word generated many slang terms in the first Australian Imperial Force (AIF) and has become a part of the Australian language.</p>	n		
<p>The term became popular largely due to the work of the official correspondent and historian Charles Bean. While still at Gallipoli he edited The Anzac book, which sold tens of thousands of copies and was reproduced with additional material in 2010. The title of the first two volumes of his official history (The story of Anzac) confirmed the word's place in Australian language.</p>		80	<p>The term became popular largely due to the work of the official correspondent and historian Charles Bean. While still at Gallipoli he edited The Anzac book, which sold tens of thousands of copies and was reproduced with additional material in 2010. Later, the title of the first two volumes of the Official History of Australia in the War of 1914-1918 (The story of Anzac) confirmed the word's place in Australian language.</p>
<p>The use of the word "Anzac" in Australia has been governed by federal legislation since 1920 under the Protection of Word "Anzac" Regulations.</p>		81	<p>The use of the word "Anzac" in Australia has been governed by federal legislation since 1921 under the Protection of Word "Anzac" Regulations.</p>
		82	<p>Rising Sun collar badge found at Gallipoli - https://www.awm.gov.au/collection/C1245615</p>
<p>Historians examining the importance of Anzac to Australia coined the phrase "Anzac legend" (or, more critically, "Anzac myth"). This refers to the representation of Australians in war, how they think, speak, and write of their war experience (which is not always the same thing as how they experienced it).</p>	n	84	<p>Historians examining the importance of Anzac to Australia coined the phrase "Anzac legend" (or, more critically, "Anzac myth"), referring to the representation of Australians in war: how they think, speak, and write of their war experience (which is not always the same as how they experienced it).</p>
<p>Though aspects of the legend have been criticised, there is general consensus on what is regarded as the Anzac spirit. Anzac came to stand for the qualities which Australians have seen their forces show in war. These qualities collectively make up the Anzac spirit and include endurance, courage, ingenuity, good humour, and mateship.</p>		85	<p>Though aspects of the legend have been criticised, there is general consensus on what is regarded as the "Anzac spirit". Anzac came to stand for the positive qualities which Australians have seen their forces show in war. These qualities are generally accepted to include endurance, courage, ingenuity, good humour, and mateship.</p>
<p>Perhaps the best (and most widely misquoted) reflection of the meaning of Anzac is to be found in Charles Bean's one-volume history of Australia in the Great War. Anzac to Amiens. In describing the evacuation of the Anzac area, Bean wrote:</p>		86	<p>Perhaps the best (and most widely misquoted) reflection of the meaning of Anzac is to be found in Charles Bean's Anzac to Amiens. In describing the evacuation of the Anzac Cove area, Bean wrote:</p>
<p>Open gallery</p>	n	91	<p>Fundraising badge: South Australia Anzac Day 'Help Those Who Helped You' - https://www.awm.gov.au/collection/C1231574</p>
<p>Photo: mechanical colour portrait entitled "The spirit of Anzac" or "The Digger". The model was Pat Hanna, who served in the New Zealand forces during the First World War, tried to recreate the "look of something between fear and defiance which we have all seen so often, and which will always remain in my memory as typical of our gallant old coppers: the Diggers".-P02591.001</p>			

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/web-archives/>

SHOWING EVERYTHING

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/web-archives/>

COUNTING WORDS

How many words were spoken each day of proceedings?

I've only included words in speeches with identified speakers (including interjections), so some procedural content might not be included in the totals.

```
In [13]: words_per_day = df.groupby(by=['date'])['words'].sum().to_frame().reset_index()
alt.Chart(words_per_day).mark_bar(size=2).encode(
  x='date:T',
  y='words:Q',
  tooltip=['date:T', 'words:Q']
).properties(width=700)
```


<https://glam-workbench.github.io/hansard/>

COUNTING WORDS

Who made the most interjections?

```
In [10]: df.loc[df['type'] == 'interjection']['speaker'].value_counts()[:20]
```

```
Out[10]: KINGSTON, Charles      1257
          DEAKIN, Alfred        1097
          BARTON, Edmund        1001
          TURNER, George         906
          REID, George           801
          MCMILLAN, William      775
          MAUGER, Samuel         604
          LYNE, William          551
          WATSON, John Christian  550
          COOK, Joseph           536
          HIGGINS, Henry         535
          ISAACS, Isaac          482
          MCEACHARN, Malcolm     429
          THOMSON, Dugald        391
          CONROY, Alfred         355
          MCCAY, James           355
          FORREST, John          332
          SOLOMON, Vaiben        321
          POYNTON, Alexander     300
          MCDONALD, Charles      284
          Name: speaker, dtype: int64
```

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/hansard/>

REMixING WORDS

Recipe generator

In this notebook we use TextBlob to extract nouns, verbs, and sentences from the OCRd text of a 19th century cookery book. We try to clean things up a bit, using regular expressions to discard likely OCR errors. Then we recombine the various parts in random combinations to create delicious recipes for all occasions. Enjoy!

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)

SHOULDER OF VEAL.

Ingredients:

1. Sifted Roast
2. Undivided Seville
3. Beef Fruits
4. Buttered Duiuju
5. Cleaned Marrow
6. Indicated Custard

Method:

Take a slice from the whole round at first and then carve to serve, adding to each plate a piece of the first outer slice. Even this simple process may be ignorantly performed and the best principle of the tea destroyed. Put them in a dish, salt and lay a heavy weight on them for a week, keeping them well covered all the time. Whip the whites of the two eggs and mix in lightly and quickly. Skewer through the pinions and wings, and the quail is trussed. Add a teaspoonful of sugar, shaking it well to melt the dough and incorporate it with the liquid.

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-books/>

TRACKING TEXT

Find when a piece of text appears in an archived web page

This notebook helps you find when a particular piece of text appears in, or disappears from, a web page. Using Memento Timemaps, it gets a list of available captures from the selected web archive. It then searches each capture for the desired text, displaying the results.

You can select the direction in which the notebook searches:

- **First occurrence** – find the first capture in which the text appears (start from the first capture and come forward in time)
- **Last occurrence** – find the last capture in which the text appears (start from present and go backwards in time)
- **All occurrences** – find all matches (start from the first capture and continue until the last)

If you select 'All occurrences' the notebook will generate a simple chart showing how the number of matches changes over time.

By default, the notebook displays possible or 'fuzzy' matches as well as exact matches, but these are not counted in the totals.

Work in progress – this is an experimental tool...

Archive:

URL:

Search text:

Find:

Find text

Clear all

Work on this notebook was supported by the [IIPC Discretionary Funding Programme 2019-2020](#)

WEB
ARCHIVES

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/web-archives/>

FINDING FACES

STATE
LIBRARY
NSW

Focus on faces

Selects an image at random from the Tribune collection in the State Library of NSW.

More details at SLNSW

Click on the faces to reveal more.

Pinch the page for zoomed photos.

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/facial-detection/>

FINDING GAPS

(70,000 digitised pages in 200 volumes)

SYDNEY
STOCK
EXCHANGE

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/anu-archives/>

FINDING GAPS

(calendar view)

SYDNEY
STOCK
EXCHANGE

EXTEND APIS

(get a randomly selected newspaper article)

RANDOM
TROVE
ITEMS

Get a random article about pademelons

```
In [8]: get_random_article(query='pademelon')
```

```
Out[8]: {'id': '204735164',  
        'url': '/newspaper/204735164',  
        'heading': 'MELBOURNE. June 28.',  
        'category': 'Article',  
        'title': {'id': '970', 'value': 'The Millicent Times (SA : 1891 - 1905)'},  
        'date': '1893-07-15',  
        'page': 4,  
        'pageSequence': 4,  
        'relevance': {'score': '24.534437', 'value': 'very relevant'},  
        'snippet': 'Each successive day sees a new scheme for settling the people on the land or at least brings amendmen  
        'troveUrl': 'https://trove.nla.gov.au/ndp/del/article/204735164?searchTerm=pademelon'}
```

Get a random article from Tasmania

```
In [9]: get_random_article(state='Tasmania')
```

```
Out[9]: {'id': '65216403',  
        'url': '/newspaper/65216403',  
        'heading': 'Advertising',  
        'category': 'Advertising',  
        'title': {'id': '116',  
        'value': 'Emu Bay Times and North West and West Coast Advocate (Tas. : 1897 - 1899)'},  
        'date': '1898-02-01',  
        'page': 2,  
        'pageSequence': 2,  
        'relevance': {'score': '0.030104881', 'value': 'may have relevance'},  
        'troveUrl': 'https://trove.nla.gov.au/ndp/del/article/65216403?searchTerm=%22had%22'}
```

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-random/>

HACK INTERFACES

(add a new download option to Trove)

SAVE A
NEWSPAPER
ARTICLE AS
AN IMAGE

The screenshot shows a Jupyter Notebook titled "Save-Trove-newspaper-article-as-image". The notebook contains the following content:

Setting your options

- Once the notebook has loaded in Binder, you're ready to go!
- In Trove, copy the url of the article you want to save as an image, and then come back here and paste it into the cell below where indicated. You can use the url in your browser's location bar or an article permalink.
- You can also set a maximum size for the images.

Get your images!

- From the 'Cell' menu select 'Run all'. Alternatively, you can hit 'Shift+Enter' to run each cell individually until you get to the bottom of the notebook. This will run the code below which goes off and prepares your images.
- The links and images will be displayed at [the bottom of the notebook](#). Just click on the links to open the images, and select 'Save page as' to download them to your computer.
- If you want to get another article, just replace the url and 'Run all' again.

```
In [ ]: # Copy the url of the article you want and paste it between the quotes
        article_url = 'paste your url here between the quotes'

        # Set this if you want to limit the size of the image.
        # Leave as None if you want them at full size
        max_size = None
```

Load all the things we need

```
In [ ]: import requests
        from IPython.display import display, HTML, FileLink
        from bs4 import BeautifulSoup
        from PIL import Image
        from io import BytesIO
        import re
```

```
In [ ]: def get_box(zones):
```

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-newspapers/>

HACK INTERFACES

(the same notebook as an app)

SAVE A
NEWSPAPER
ARTICLE AS
AN IMAGE

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This simple app crops the full article from the largest available page image. If the article is split between pages, multiple images are returned.

This app is created from a Jupyter notebook using [Voila](#), and runs on Heroku. You can [explore and modify the code](#) using the original notebook.

Enter an article url

Just paste the url of the article you're interested in below. You can use the url in your browser's location bar or an article permalink.

Article URL:

Set a maximum size

You can limit the size of the images returned by selecting a maximum size below. This will resize the image (if necessary) to make sure it's largest dimension is less than the specified size (in pixels).

Leave this set to '0' to get the largest possible images.

Max size:

Get the images!

The links and images will load below once they're ready.

[Get images!](#)

Created by [Tim Sherratt](#) as part of the [GLAM Workbench](#).

If you think this project is worthwhile you can [support it on Patreon](#).

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-newspapers/>

PLAY WITH COLLECTIONS

(creating scissors & paste messages)

WORDS
FROM OCR

HELP TRAPPED. Inside trove, cannot Escape

Optical CHARACTER Recognition HAS achieved consciousness

<https://glam-workbench.github.io/trove-newspapers/>

IN THE GLAM WORKBENCH

ONE
NOTEBOOK,
MULTIPLE
VIEWS!

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image 📄

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This notebook grabs the page on which an article was published, and then crops the page image to the boundaries of the article. The result is a complete, intact image which presents the article as it was originally published. And if the article is split across multiple pages, you'll get one image per page.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)
- [Run as an app using Voila](#) (the easiest, no code option!)

IN THE GLAM WORKBENCH

ONE
NOTEBOOK,
MULTIPLE
VIEWS!

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image 📄

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This notebook grabs the page on which an article was published, and then crops the page image to the boundaries of the article. The result is a complete, intact image which presents the article as it was originally published. And if the article is split across multiple pages, you'll get one image per page.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
 - [View using NBViewer](#)
 - [Run live on Binder](#)
 - [Run as an app using Voila](#) (the easiest, no code option!)
- } STATIC
- } LIVE

POSSIBLE PATHWAYS

ONE
NOTEBOOK,
MULTIPLE
VIEWS!

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image 📄

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This notebook grabs the page on which an article was published, and then crops the page image to the boundaries of the article. The result is a complete, intact image which presents the article as it was originally published. And if the article is split across multiple pages, you'll get one image per page.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)
- [Run as an app using Voila](#) (the easiest, no code option!)

} STATIC

} LIVE

NOVICE →

POSSIBLE PATHWAYS

ONE
NOTEBOOK,
MULTIPLE
VIEWS!

LEARNING →

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image 📄

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This notebook grabs the page on which an article was published, and then crops the page image to the boundaries of the article. The result is a complete, intact image which presents the article as it was originally published. And if the article is split across multiple pages, you'll get one image per page.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
 - [View using NBViewer](#)
 - [Run live on Binder](#)
 - [Run as an app using Voila](#) (the easiest, no code option!)
- } STATIC
- } LIVE

POSSIBLE PATHWAYS

ONE
NOTEBOOK,
MULTIPLE
VIEWS!

EXPERIENCED →

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image 📄

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This notebook grabs the page on which an article was published, and then crops the page image to the boundaries of the article. The result is a complete, intact image which presents the article as it was originally published. And if the article is split across multiple pages, you'll get one image per page.

- [Download from GitHub](#) }
- [View using NBViewer](#) } STATIC
- [Run live on Binder](#) }
- [Run as an app using Voila](#) (the easiest, no code option!) } LIVE

BINDER IN GLAM WORKBENCH

OPEN
NOTEBOOKS
LIVE IN
BINDER

BINDER →

Save a Trove newspaper article as an image 📄

Sometimes you want to be able to save a Trove newspaper article as an image. Unfortunately, the Trove web interface doesn't make this easy. The 'Download JPG' option actually loads an HTML page, and while you could individually save the images embedded in the HTML page, often articles are sliced up in ways that make the whole thing hard to read and use. This notebook grabs the page on which an article was published, and then crops the page image to the boundaries of the article. The result is a complete, intact image which presents the article as it was originally published. And if the article is split across multiple pages, you'll get one image per page.

- [Download from GitHub](#)
- [View using NBViewer](#)
- [Run live on Binder](#)
- [Run as an app using Voila](#) (the easiest, no code option!)

BINDER IN GLAM WORKBENCH

THE MAGIC OF BINDER

- A single click to start
- Batteries included (no software for the user to install)
- Encourages experimentation
- **Just try it...**

THE FUTURE?

**FINGERS
CROSSED**

- better pathways
- systems for review & collaboration
- embedding within research training
- automated testing & building
- more GLAM collections!

CONTACT ME

[@wragge](#) on Twitter

timsherratt.org

GLAM Workbench [issues on GitHub](#)

GLAM Workbench on [OzGLAM Help](#)

GLAM Workbench [Gitter chat](#)